

DyMoN
Dynamic Mobility Nudge

**DyMoN – Dynamic Mobility Nudge:
Shaping sustainable urban mobility behaviour with
real-time, user-generated and public open data**

Motivation for more sustainable urban mobility through digital, data-driven nudging methods

- Design of effective, data-driven, digital nudging methods for encouraging sustainable mobility
- Co-creation with city stakeholders, citizens and researchers
- Two pilot cities: Salzburg + Uppsala
- Guidance for cities with interactive dashboards, handbooks and virtual workshops

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Energy, Mobility,
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